

The Value, Purpose and Pilot Project of University Smart Sports Service System

YU SUN¹, OOI BOON KEAT ^{2*}

¹: Wuchang Shouyi University, Basic Science Department, Wuhan, Hubei Province, 430064, China.

¹: Management and Science University, Postgraduate Center, Selangor Darul Ehsan, Shah Alam, 40100, Malaysia

²: Management and Science University, Postgraduate Center, Selangor Darul Ehsan, Shah Alam, 40100, Malaysia

Abstract

To explore the value and purpose of the construction of the smart sports service system in universities, to analyze the detailed rules of the system construction through the pilot research, and to put forward the suggestions and prospects. Research results: Value mainly refers to the construction of a higher level of national fitness public service system, driving the integration and transformation of university sports service, and improving the participation of teachers and students through efficient supply. The basic purpose include local conditions, people-oriented, on-demand configuration and green

innovation; The system construction is mainly reflected in the comprehensive construction of smart stadiums, ecological layout, platform service and background management. In view of the development of smart sports into university sports service and combined with the development status of smart sports industry, this paper puts forward some feasible suggestions. Looking into the future, science and technology will enable universities to build a smart sports service system with a higher level, wider dimension and deeper integration.

Keywords: Smart sports; Service system; National fitness; Health communication

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years under the background of COVID-19 outbreak, local universities strictly implement the normalized epidemic prevention and control measures, but under the long period closed management, guarantee the rigid demand, domestic universities generally face multiple difficulties to be solved, such as "how to meet the diversity of physical activity and spiritual

communication demands", "how to guide students out of the information cocoon room, active into the health environment", etc. The solution to the dilemma is not only to empower students with individual epidemic prevention, but also to implement the national strategy of national fitness and achieve the fundamental goal of national health. The construction of campus health service is a basic project directly related to problem solving and strategy implementation. Accelerating the formation of a strong campus health service ecosystem is a necessary move to do a good job in promoting students' health (Chen, 2022). Science and technology, as the first productive force, is also the way to solve the problem of demand. In recent years, the wave of information technology has swept the world. The rapid development of the Internet of Things, big data, cloud computing, 5G and other new technologies has drawn a new development prospect for the field of sports. Sports need to keep up with the pace of the development of information technology and explore a new road of integration and transformation, and smart sports is imperative. From the outbreak during the home during class, micro, live class and other different forms of online teaching platform success, to 5G technology in Beijing Olympic venues, the universiade intelligent venues show science and technology, ecology, culture "broken" interaction, to Shanghai, Wuxi, Chongqing and other cities wisdom sports service construction, the display of many classic cases to "wisdom sports" natural behavior to the construction of health services, become the implementation of the national fitness strategy, but also to the society from all walks of life to reveal technology can assign service, sports wisdom has become the future trend. In the future, the construction of national fitness space will be promoted with "wisdom" in an all-round and multi-dimensional way. The smart sports industry will continue to explore new scenes of national fitness and promote the quality and upgrading of sports public services (Huang, 2020). The word "service" itself is an economic term. When the combination of "wisdom", "sports" and "service" will bring great changes to both ends of the supply and demand of the sports service environment in universities, and impact the traditional single, loose and fragmented sports service mode and structure of universities (Xie et al., 2022). Based on the empowerment of science and technology and demand orientation, this paper plans to build the smart sports service system in universities, carry out the integration and reasonable utilization of various campus resources according to local conditions, deeply explore the function value and intrinsic value of sports, and drive the sustainable development of humanistic service and ecological civilization in universities with wisdom as the core.

2. Theory of value and purpose

Different from the traditional university physical education activities, the essential difference of smart sports services in universities lies in the empowerment of "wisdom" (Zhu, 2021). The original intention of "wisdom" is "an advanced comprehensive ability based on neural organs", including perceptual discrimination, logical reasoning, judgment and decision

making, etc. The Cambridge Dictionary defines "wisdom" as the ability to make appropriate decisions using knowledge or experience. Traditional philosophy holds that "wisdom" is "clear method channel", "wisdom" of IBM wisdom earth means "thorough perception, ubiquitous interconnection and intelligent integration", "wisdom" comes from the information technology, refers to the use of advanced ideas and technical means to create intelligent learning environment to form a precise, individual and flexible education service system (Cao,2018). Thus, it can be seen that although "wisdom" has different structures, "wisdom" first represents the positive and innovative comprehensive ability outside, and inside is the value understanding and moral identity of good and common good. University wisdom sports service is an organic part of the wisdom education service system, from the perspective of education informatization, university wisdom sports service "wisdom" is a kind of "wisdom" technology, is based on 5G, chain blocks, Internet of things, big data, artificial intelligence and other modern information technology platform and environment, man-machine synergy advanced technology (see Figure 1) (Li et al., 2020). It is embodied in: (1) creating an immersive motion virtual scene. It not only effectively solves the bottleneck of insufficient equipment allocation and site safety risk of various sports projects in universities, but also allows learners to be immersive and completely immersed in the vivid sports scene image world. (2) Laying the learning path of three-dimensional technology. With the help of various wearable devices, students expand the input source of movement information through the application of computing and service models, generate the quantitative basis for teaching diagnosis and feedback of university physical education courses, and boost the formation of multi-dimensional perception and three-dimensional learning channels. (3) Stimulate the cool and cool interactive sports experience. The new research and development of various intelligent sports products and services for university students' consumers makes them continuously achieve technological breakthroughs in user experience, sports logic and interface beauty, and make the interactive sports experience a reality (Jing et al., 2019).

THE VALUE, PURPOSE AND PILOT PROJECT OF UNIVERSITY SMART SPORTS SERVICE SYSTEM

Figure 1 The "wisdom" deconstruction of smart sports service in universities

Source: Adapted from Li et al., (2021)

From the perspective of the essence of education service, the "intelligent core" of smart sports service in universities is a kind of "humanistic wisdom". Its education service object sports demand as the core, through the service form, service content, service function of system change, and provide the most need, the most suitable, the most accurate and most convenient personalized sports teaching service, health management services, reveal the people-oriented service theme, embodied in: (1) The openness of the form of service. With the support of modern information technology, teachers and students in universities only need to hold the seamless connection and mutual integration of intelligent terminals to the intelligent sports service platform, an open, collaborative and shared central system, to obtain "menu" sports resources and services freely and efficiently, freely and efficiently, so that sports are everywhere. (2) The wide extension of the service content. From the perspective of content scope, the content of smart sports service covers online and offline integrated physical education course teaching, sports community interaction, intelligent venue management and other multidimensional needs. In terms of the depth of content, the output of teaching skills of physical education courses is more full and vivid under the condition of three-dimensional multi-perception technology of language, image and emotional consciousness, which can make the sports experience under the resonance of sports thinking and sports psychological immersion more profound. (3) Integration of service functions. Through the application of intelligent technology and information technology, it fully excavates and analyzes the fully recorded data information and automatically generates suitable personalized services, so as to meet the differentiated sports needs of students; through the physiological indicators such as

heart rate, blood pressure, pulse oxygen saturation and portable on, so as to realize the scientific normal prevention and control of students' sports risk.

Therefore, the smart sports service in universities is the smart upgrade of the traditional sports service in universities, which is a new mode of sports service with both "technological wisdom" and "humanistic wisdom". Among them, "technical wisdom" is the basic support, which is the necessary condition for the change of university sports service form, service content and service function in the intelligent era; and "humanistic wisdom" is the fundamental starting point of the reform of university sports service system in the intelligent era (Wang et al., 2019). Therefore, the smart sports service in universities is a human-machine collaborative service represented by the comprehensive and in-depth application of 5G, blockchain, Internet of Things, big data, artificial intelligence in the field of public sports in universities, and the physical education activities centering on the needs of students' physical education. As a new service mode, it is committed to realizing a wider range of sports participation, more human-oriented sports experience, more accurate health management and more three-dimensional sports communication, which represents the development direction of sports innovation in universities in the intelligent era (Yu, 2017).

2.1 The value of building the smart sports service system in universities

2.1.1 Build a higher level of public service system for national fitness

The healthy China strategy should be based on building a higher level of national fitness public service system (Yang, 2022). In 2022, the general office of the central committee of the communist party of China, the General Office of the State Council issued "about building a higher level of national fitness opinions of public service system" (hereinafter referred to as the "opinions"), requires each unit to implement sports activities promotion plan, build a higher level of the national fitness service system, which fit the masses of the people, especially under the closed management by the winter Olympics, winter paralympic games and the universiade competition spirit radiation of university students. In recent years, the government has issued such as "healthy China 2030" planning outline "healthy China action (2019-2030)" the "difference" sports development plan, etc., are emphatically promote the national fitness service system, a series of policy documents fully embodies the government to achieve high level of national fitness public service system attaches great importance to and strategic initiative. Policy is the focus of the implementation, the traditional campus health service system to upgrade, and accordingly adhering to the "opinion" "outline" action "planning" documents such as program of action and the concept of construction, in view of the current university students reality demands build differentiation and synergy of university wisdom sports service system, from the diversification of participants, supply content diversification and service mode innovation confirms it is further, a higher level of the national fitness public service system (Li & Li, 2022).

2.1.2 Drive the integration and transformation of sports service channels in universities

At present, smart sports is still a relatively young concept. As an internal deepening of smart city, it is based on the technology empowerment of the information age and includes the concept of smart city in the sports field of extension, which is a senior ecosystem of "technology + concept". The concrete and vivid case is that the recent technology proposed by the "Science and technology Winter Olympics" benefits life, and the joint construction of intelligent sports venues advocated by the Universiade Park combined with ecological civilization (Li et al., 2018). Driving the integration of smart sports into campus services is also to build such a new future-oriented model, not by an embedded development on the original basis, but by a broken shape from the inside out. Externally, scientific and technological innovation and technology diffusion provide good external opportunities for the integration of smart sports into campus; while internally, the integration of smart sports at the beginning of the construction will promote the high-quality development of campus service, and the development of campus service reflects the high-quality life of university students after the completion of the system, students' realistic demands are high-quality life, the consistency of the two goals means the perfect docking of ideas, and creates a harmonious internal environment for the smooth integration of smart sports. The smooth completion of campus smart sports service system has impacted the traditional health service ecology of universities, and will change subversive from management to supply: breaking the block division of sports resources, from "decentralized" to "integrated" to normal management; the health service supply can be reformed on the basis of sufficient mode, from "inclusive" to "comprehensive" to provide students with personalized, intelligent, flexible and comprehensive services. Promoting smart sports rooted in the campus is committed to creating a high-quality development case in the national fitness cause, pointing out the road of integration and transformation for the university sports service system, and boosting the high-quality development of the smart sports industry (Chen, 2022).

2.1.3 Improve the sports participation of teachers and students through efficient supply

Empirical studies in psychology show that motivation has an initial effect on behavior, driving an individual to produce a certain behavior (Chen, 2022). Under the control of the school closure, the internal driving force of physical activity of teachers and students has been fully mobilized, and what is lacking is the incentive to stimulate the motivation of teachers and students — good health communication environment and efficient sports resource supply. In this regard, the smart sports service system of universities provides virtual community and information feedback through the service platform, and jointly builds a good health communication environment combined with the healthy supporting environment of real space transformation to ensure the efficient supply of campus sports resources (Liu, 2021). As a

vertical platform for information sharing and real-time interaction, Serving the campus users based on the decentralized communication context, "Cofrequency resonance" with the offline health support environment, After fully integrating the value of the Internet of Things, the Internet, big data and other information technologies, Presentation is to break the space limit —— Real space is fully eliminated on the smart sports service platform of universities, Virtual community, information feedback and other functional services effectively shorten the distance between people, people and things; Breaking down time limit —— Health supportive environment reconstructed the use time of teachers and students for university sports resources, Realize the venue resources and outdoor resources are open to the same all day long. In addition, a few university students with very low participation of sports, such as information cocoon and lack of sports awareness, are the key groups of attention in university physical education. A good communication environment and health supportive environment can effectively awaken the internal driving force of people to participate in physical activities, and promote this group to actively integrate into sports. The continuous interaction between internal driving force and inducement stimulates individual strong sports motivation, and the efficient supply of sports resources ensures the sports participation of all teachers and students, and then achieves the fundamental goal of all teachers and students' fitness and health of all teachers and students in the campus (Gong, 2021).

2.2. Purpose of building a smart sports service system in universities

2.2.1 Adjust measures to local conditions

The traditional layout of campus resources in domestic universities presents a block distribution, there is a broken boundary between sports resources and natural resources, and there is no obvious development connection between the two sides (Zheng, 2022). The block distribution of resource strips also divides the campus service system from the whole into parts. The key step to realize the organic integration of campus humanistic services and natural resources is to integrate resources according to local conditions and make scientific and reasonable layout. The so-called measures according to local conditions, scientific and reasonable refers to the adjustment and transformation based on the actual construction of campus resources at the current stage, taking into account the spatial layout needs of the joint development of sports resources and natural resources, and different regions have clear service functions. At the same time, universities actively explore their transformation focus, highlight the regional characteristics of the campus to ensure the campus service system has long potential, the university of York based on the healthy supportive environment of "edible campus" activities, Xiamen university based on the traditional feng shui culture "four spirit around" "tai chi" Yin and Yang " combined with discipline characteristics of xiang'an campus, can be listed as adjust measures to local conditions in universities, scientific layout of learning case (Zhong, 2019).

2.2.2 People oriented

At the National Health and Health Conference, General Secretary Xi Jinping specifically pointed out that to promote the construction of a healthy China, we must firmly give priority to the people's health development (Liu, 2022). Wisdom university sports service system to build the purpose of pay attention to from the perspective of "people-oriented", lay the students as the principal position of campus health services, in the service supply area continuously permeate the idea of "health first", build all students widely participate in the campus sports atmosphere, let the students clear "health first responsibility" to belong to itself. System based on fitness and health depth fusion on the basis of health supportive environment, with simple and convenient, comprehensive coverage of indoor and outdoor service mode to solve students 'physical activity and spiritual communication reality, attract students out of the information cocoon room, gradually improve students' fitness participation, cultivate students' active health consciousness, promote students actively into the campus environment. It can be said that the smart sports service system in universities not only continues the traditional Chinese education concept, but also implements the "health first" thought of health work and physical education in universities in the new era.

2.2.3 Configure on demand

Under the pressure of the epidemic, people's demand for sports and fitness presents a blowout explosion, and the application of science and technology will become a key node to balance supply and demand (Huang, 2022). Demand on the growing university supply side cannot effectively match, and cities, the community of the national fitness resources supply problems, the campus health resources supply also exist uneven distribution, such as single problem, under the national fitness career trend, university wisdom sports service system demand oriented, with "wisdom" as the center, provide simple and quick comprehensive service, venue facilities and spiritual communication two aspects of architecture in order to maintain equal campus health services, standardization, diversified supply. On the one hand, the construction of intelligent sports venues and facilities commensurate with the number of students, the expansion of the supply side will in turn stimulate the demand side, while the construction of sports resources, jointly promote the construction of outdoor ecological civilization. On the other hand, after the completion of the facilities, the sports competitions and health activities will be carried out regularly, and the communication functional area will be opened on the service platform, so as to enhance students 'participation in sports projects and the experience of sports process and meet students' spiritual communication demands.

2.2.4 Green innovation

Different from the traditional sports services provided by universities, the campus smart

sports service system essentially overthrew the traditional model and establishes an innovative mode with the development characteristics of the "14th Five-Year Plan" period with "innovation" and "green" as the theme words (Zhu et al., 2023). Development concept is the forerunner of development practice, build campus wisdom sports service system to "wisdom" as the kernel drive, through the Internet, Internet, big data and other information technology integration to build intelligent sports venues, online information feedback mechanism, virtual interpersonal interaction community, intelligent popularization to students, and in the future operation process into the new technology, make "innovation" wisdom endogenous sports service of campus system. Green building materials and renewable energy should be used in venues and outdoor construction, and the new layout of campus natural resources and sports resources should be coordinated according to population elements, so as to realize the harmonious coexistence of ecological civilization and humanistic services and maintain sustainable development.

3. Methods and conclusions of the pilot research

As to overturn the traditional sports service mode innovation ecological system, the construction of university wisdom sports service system reflects the information age advanced technology and health supportive environment "symbiotic interdependence", through the deep online business scenarios and offline movement scene, based on a variety of information technology intervention campus reality regional space, generate network virtual service platform, with the network as the medium to connect both linkage development in the same system (Lu, 2022).

A certain campus existing campus sports service mode in line with the typical traditional sports service supply mode, the single, loose, fragmentation of sports service mode and structure caused the imbalance between supply and demand, and cause the campus sports management mechanism is not sound, difficult to take effect, the problem of existing feedback information is system reform, to clarify the value of intelligent sports service system and basic purpose corresponding to explain the necessity and importance of reconstruction system (Zhang et al., 2019). Wisdom city, wisdom community has clarified sports wisdom will promote the development of the national fitness high quality, wisdom in university sports service system, students through the network virtual service platform for sports wisdom service, will meet their use for sports venues, human-computer interaction, activities and competition demand, improve the utilization of campus sports, natural resources, effectively contribute to the campus idle resources and service level to upgrade.

3.1 Intelligent ecological layout

The artificial lake is located in the central area of the campus, and its area and terrain and the existing construction are extremely in line with the characteristics of small parks. It is

THE VALUE, PURPOSE AND PILOT PROJECT OF UNIVERSITY SMART SPORTS SERVICE SYSTEM

feasible to make the layout according to the functional zoning of the city park (see Figure 2). The side of the artificial lake adjacent to the teaching area is the only place that teachers and students must pass through during the class period. With the influence of the learning atmosphere in the teaching area, it is built into a sports culture corridor, aiming to popularize the history of sports and promote the spirit of sports. The environment above the corridor is quiet, and the terrain is layered, and a certain number of pavilions, tables and stools are added, in the name of "academic exchange (problem discussion, tea party, etc.), leisure and entertainment (chess and cards, games, etc.)", to expand the available space of the campus with simple changes. The island on the other side of the corridor is flat, and a certain number of park fitness equipment is added to create outdoor fitness area, develop various ways for students to do outdoor sports. Outdoor running has always been one of the main sports methods for university students, and night running is the sport with the highest participation of most university students. The artificial lake smart track is equipped with a large smart screen in the outdoor fitness area. Students can log in with the account of the service platform. The smart track is equipped with a face recognition bar without wearing hardware equipment. In addition, the artificial lake smart track connects the three functional areas according to the trend of the coast, and the surrounding natural environment and the terrain slope also provide participants with a realistic outdoor running experience. The layout transformation of the artificial lake makes the campus leisure sports center become a healthy supporting environment integrating four elements of culture, leisure, sports and science and technology, and truly achieve the same functional service level as the city sports park.

Figure 2 Concept of ecological layout of artificial lake

3.2 Smart sports stadiums

Smart stadiums are typical representative works of the deep integration of information

technology and sports physical buildings. Different from the traditional stadiums in universities, which basically focus on physical space, the intelligent transformation of stadiums under the smart sports service system pays more attention to the construction of environment and service (Zhao et al., 2023). As one of the venues for the 31st Summer Universiade, a campus has achieved the completeness of sports stadium resources through active renovation. On the basis of integrating existing resources, it uses science and technology to carry out the integrated transformation of sports venues from the outside and the inside. First of all, the combination of access control equipment and face recognition, linkage temperature measurement and code scanning technology realizes non-influence admission, to ensure that the abnormal in public places refuse to enter the epidemic, and mark and lock the background of the abnormal feedback system to "send to the hospital" in time. Secondly, automatic induction devices, such as intelligent light control and temperature control, are installed inside the site to achieve reasonable and economical use; exclusive cameras in different venues can capture the wonderful moments of sports participants and provide personalized services; intelligent wearable equipment, such as watches and wristbands, selectively worn by sports participants, can monitor, record and upload the physiological changes and exercise data of sports participants in real time to ensure the safety of the exercise process. Finally, through face recognition, intelligent monitoring and system data monitoring, users are early warned and traced accountable (see Figure 3).

3.3 Intelligent platform service

Online platform services to "a homepage four plates", a home page after the user login client "I" interface, four plates, in turn, for intelligent fitness, information feedback, exercise prescription, virtual community, in addition to the virtual community is a comprehensive service plate, the other three plate function directivity, the supply of service content are based on the same logic. From the perspective of information technology architecture, the motion data is derived from zero to some, and it has four levels: the basic layer is acquired through sensing and identification technologies; the network layer uses Internet and mobile communication network technologies; the computing layer classifies, analyzes and mines, and the application layer uses artificial intelligence and other technologies. The division of labor of the four levels is clear. "Basic layer-network layer-computing layer-application layer" corresponds to the service mechanism of "perception-transmission-processing-generation" (see Figure 3). The content construction of "one home page and four plates" makes the online service platform become a we-media platform. Users can obtain the service content only by "one click". Based on the user's use process, the functions of the four sections are interlinked to form a "service loop" (see Figure 4): (1) Intelligent fitness. Provide online real-time query of venue situation, venue reservation and other functions to solve the pain point of user information asymmetry, and further improve the introduction of social relationship chain such

THE VALUE, PURPOSE AND PILOT PROJECT OF UNIVERSITY SMART SPORTS SERVICE SYSTEM

as friend view, male to female ratio; (2) Information feedback. The user's exercise data will be divided into two parts of transmission —— platform backup and self-viewing. The information feedback section analyzes the physiological changes such as heart rate fluctuation and heat consumption during the exercise process on the basis of the data. The review after the exercise is conducive to advance planning of the exercise load, time and supply for the user to participate in again; (3) exercise prescription. After the first authorization and automatic data uploading, the intelligent system starts the processing of personal movement data for one or more backups. After data to user portrait, analysis of preferences, mining needs and classification attributes, it automatically generates personalized movement guidance prescriptions. (4) virtual community. Sports partners matching, sports achievement sharing, personal experience, health knowledge, campus sports information release, sports activities and competitions are the service content of the plate, at the beginning of the university wisdom sports service system construction, virtual community with diverse comprehensive service content as accelerating promote campus health communication and the important means of health promotion work.

Figure 3 Overall structure diagram of the smart sports service system in universities

Figure 4 Closed-loop diagram of smart sports service supply in universities

3.4 Intelligent management mode

The establishment of the smart sports service system in universities announces that the traditional management mode is replaced by the intelligent management mode, which is mainly reflected in the two aspects (see Figure 3). First, venue management. Traditional university sports venues by "one pavilion" or "one pavilion people" is responsible for the operations, management staff in mechanical repetitive work process, emergency response and coordinate venues, long so exposed the disadvantages is high operating costs and low efficiency, wisdom sports service under the system of management mode to realize the full digital, unmanned management, solve the disadvantages also let students avoid to participate in sports temperature measurement, registration, lights even peak queue such as cumbersome process. Second, data management. Service platform of data management library efficiently solve the demand side and supply side large diverse information display, storage, classification, changed the traditional management mode of people and things as the center of data processing, a variety of information technology collaboration service platform can be fast and convenient, orderly processing four plate service content, the background managers only regular check, to ensure the normal operation of the system.

4. Suggestions

This paper fully takes into account the development constraints of smart sports integration into campus sports service, combined with the development status of smart sports industry, and puts forward the following suggestions for the construction of smart sports service system in universities:

- (1) Follow the national standards closely. Follow the national policy guidance, implement

THE VALUE, PURPOSE AND PILOT PROJECT OF UNIVERSITY SMART SPORTS SERVICE SYSTEM

the national strategy of healthy China and national fitness, and closely follow the guidance of national construction standards;

(2) School-enterprise collaborative management. Advocate the management mode of school-enterprise cooperation, each performing his own duties and showing his strengths;

(3) Pay attention to service experience. The word "service" through the wisdom sports into the global construction, the current wisdom sports service system construction still need to focus on the service construction, pay attention to the use of students experience, on the basis of consolidating the existing service level, the demand according to the development of new business, provide students with more personalized, standardized, intelligent service function;

(4) Formulate system standards. Government departments should build the standard system of smart sports industry, promote the standardization construction, so that the smart sports industry has rules to follow in the process of operation, management and service, accelerate technological innovation, and then promote the process of integrating smart sports into the campus;

(5) Set up the prevention mechanism. The security protection of students' personal privacy data is the common responsibility of the relevant government departments and universities. The government jointly focus on the risk prevention mechanism of students' privacy data in advance, and preset the remedial measures after the event, taking students' information security as the first element;

(6) Promoting both internal and external unified progress. universities in the same region should make unified planning, promote the whole way, realize the sharing of resources, data and experience, break the information island, and adopt the advanced and backward way when necessary. At the same time, the internal construction system of universities to achieve "three unification", that is, unified construction, unified operation, unified maintenance;

(7) Early transboundary integration. With technological innovation, the production end will cover the whole campus application system platform, campus wisdom construction by decentralized construction "integration mode" towards the unified platform of "concentrated mode" transformation, under this trend, the wisdom sports service system should realize interdisciplinary integration as early as possible, for example has the body of medical integration wisdom service system, to provide a more comprehensive service content.

5. Outlook

At present, the sports science and technology industry will 5G, artificial intelligence, AI has great development potential of new technology into the wisdom sports field for deeper practice, diverse research achievements, such as man-machine versus, virtual factory imagine things into reality, its social value highlights in gradually realize technology comprehensive benefit people's life, all areas for people's life quality upgrade (Wang & Xu, 2021). In the future, wisdom sports fully integrated into the school, science and technology can assign universities

THE VALUE, PURPOSE AND PILOT PROJECT OF UNIVERSITY SMART SPORTS SERVICE SYSTEM

build up a higher level, more wide dimension, deeper integration of sports service system, in multiple levels of various conditions meet the increasing demand of students, and as the industry technology innovation and reasonable cost, artificial intelligence teachers field teaching, AR virtual classroom online learning, intelligent robot training, intelligent referee cutting become normal campus, realize the digital sports teaching, training and service of disruptive change. Wisdom sports service system of good operation and mature development, build the campus health communication environment, promote students with healthy behavior to build health at the same time, will also run with wisdom community, wisdom city rail, promote each other, promote the national fitness and national health depth fusion, power health China strategy as soon as possible.

REFERENCES:

- Cao, P. J. (2018). Intelligent education: Educational change in the era of artificial intelligence. *Educational Research*, 39(8), 121-128.
- Chen, W. (2022). Teacher's idea conflict and behavior Generation in classroom teaching reform. Doctoral dissertation, Urumqi: Xinjiang Normal University.
- Chen, Y. D. (2022). Research on the construction and promotion strategy of Community Smart Sports Service System in Anhui Province. Doctoral dissertation, Beijing: Beijing Sport University.
- Gong, Q. B. (2021). Research on University students' sports participation from the perspective of social ecology. Doctoral dissertation, Shanghai: Shanghai University of Sport.
- Huang, H. Y. (2020). Strategic thinking on promoting sports industry to become the pillar industry of national economy. *China Sport Science*, 40(12), 3-16.
- Huang, H. Y. (2022). Sports industry in the process of Chinese modernization: Development trend and reform path. *Journal of Xi'an Physical Education University*, 39(6), 526-536.
- Jing, W., Li, Y. & Liu, Y. G. (2019). Research on the ubiquitous new sports learning Mode Under the background of "Internet + Education". *Journal of Physical Education*, 26(1), 120-124.
- Li, Y. Y., Chen, W., & Wu, X. L. (2021). The logic implication, system construction and operation guarantee of intelligent sports service in universities in the intelligent era. *Journal of Wuhan Institute of Physical Education*, 55(12), 35-42.
- Li, Y. Z., Zhou, Q., & Zhao, J. (2018). Reflections on the construction of intelligent campus in universities. *China Educational Technology*, 1, 112-117.
- Li, Z. J., & Li, Z. X. (2022). Smart Sports: Characteristics, development dilemma and promotion path. *Journal of Shenyang Institute of Physical Education*, 41(4), 64-70.
- Liu, M. L. (2021). Research on intelligent Ideological and political Construction in Universities under the background of artificial Intelligence. Doctoral dissertation, Taiyuan:

Shanxi Normal University.

- Liu, T. (2022). Research on the educational value and realization path of school space. Doctoral dissertation, Guilin: Guangxi Normal University.
- Lu, C., Wu, Y. D. & Zheng, C. H. (2022). The enlightenment of the design concept of the International Paralympic Committee accessibility Guide to the Beijing Winter Paralympic Games. *Journal of Xi'an Physical Education University*, 39(1), 31-39.
- Wang, H. R., Zhao, H. H. & Yu, J. B. (2019). Current situation analysis and development countermeasure of Sports curriculum construction of Chinese University MOOC. *Journal of Wuhan Sports University*, 53(8), 69-75.
- Wang, Y. & Xu, X. H. (2021). Exploration of new business forms and ethical dilemmas of sports culture communication in the 5G era. *Journal of Beijing Sport University*, 44(7), 132-142.
- Xie, B., Zhao, Z. P., & Zhang, H. (2022). The value implication, basic principle and system construction of intelligent sports service system in universities. *Bulletin of Sport Science & Technology*, 30(11), 133-137.
- Yang, G. Q. (2022). New thinking on accelerating the construction of a strong sports country in the process of Chinese-style modernization. *Journal of Tianjin University of Sport*, 37(6), 664-671.
- Yu, S. M. (2017). Construction of the framework system of Chinese students' physical education core accomplishment. *Journal of Physical Education*, 24(4), 5-9.
- Zhang, D., Qu, L. P. & Zhang, J. H. (2019). Construction and optimization of ecological security pattern based on the perspective of ecological supply and demand: A case study of the Yangtze River Delta. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 39(20), 7525-7537.
- Zhao, X. H., Xie, L. W., Zhu, Y. J. & Wang, M. Z. (2023). The research hotspot, course evolution and development trend analysis of smart sports in our country. *Hubei Sports Science*, 42(04), 311-319.
- Zheng, B. B. (2022). Construction and realization path of intelligent governance system for sports public service resource sharing. *Journal of Weinan Normal University*, 37(8), 48-54.
- Zhong, G. D. (2019). Research on the framework of government smart Governance and its economic effectiveness Measurement in the era of Big Data. Doctoral dissertation, Wuhan: Wuhan University.
- Zhu, C. G., Guo, X. J., Wang, K., Wang, J., Liu, H. J., Liu, L. & Che, B. Q. (2023). Research on Chinese style sports modernization. *Journal of Sports Research*, 37(1), 1-14.
- Zhu, Z. T. (2021). Intelligent education leads the innovation of school education in the future. *Journal of Schooling Studies*, 18(2), 5-20.